

APPLICATION OF EXTRACELLULAR VESICLES OBTAINED FROM PLANTS IN VARIOUS DISEASE

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ABSTRACT

Extracellular vesicles (EVs) aid in repair and regeneration processes by delivering biomolecules and cellular components to damaged cells or tissues. Plant EVs were first discovered in 1967, before mammalian EVs, and although they resemble mammalian EVs, they differ in the composition of their metabolites. As diseases increase rapidly, the need for natural treatments increases. Therefore, emphasis is placed on exosome therapies, one of the new methods. There is various information about plant-derived EVs in the literature. We have not come across any research on this topic in our country. Therefore, our goal in this article was to demonstrate the importance of EVs obtained from various plants by examining and analyzing the therapeutic effects of EVs in diseases in the literature. The results of the analyses showed that, due to their non-immunogenicity, low toxicity, high delivery efficiency, and good biocompatibility, plant-derived EVs can be used as a new type of carrier for the delivery of intracellular substances such as nucleic acids, active lipids, and cellular proteins, as well as for the delivery of extracellular proteins and small molecule drugs. We can also see in these analyses that plant-derived EVs have antiviral and anti-inflammatory effects, modulate detoxification enzymes, and stimulate the immune response.

Keywords: extracellular vesicles, diseases, anti-inflammatory, macrophages, antimicrobial effect, antioxidant effect.

Introduction

Extracellular vesicles (EVs) are small extracellular bubbles released into the environment by cells. Different cell types are also secreted by prokaryotic and eukaryotic cells, and consist of bilayer phospholipid membranes ranging in diameter from 30 to 2000 nm [1].

Extracellular vesicles of mammalian origin are found in body fluids such as plasma, cerebrospinal fluid, urine, saliva, amniotic fluid, colostrum, breast milk, synovial fluid, semen, and pleural fluid[2].

EV numbers in body fluids are significantly enriched compared to other cells and can act as an independent diagnostic biomarker.

Extracellular vesicles can be divided into 3 main classes [3,4].

Exosomes - Exosomes are naturally occurring biological nanoparticles that form intercellular communication, ranging in size from 30 to 120 nm. They are produced by endosomes within the cell [5].

Microvesicles - Size 100-1000 nm. Formed by bulging of the cell membrane [6].

Apoptotic bodies - Their size is 500-2000nm. They are formed during cell apoptosis (cell death).

They are released by cellular exocytosis and contain genetic molecules (DNA or RNA), proteins, and other bioactive substances. These vesicles play a role in various biological processes and form an important part of the cellular communication system. EVs transmit information between cells, which plays an important role in various physiological and pathological processes, and also participates in the regulation of the immune response. EVs aid in repair and regeneration processes by delivering biomolecules and cellular components to damaged cells or tissues. In general, EVs play an important role in the regulation of numerous physiological

and pathological processes at the cellular and tissue levels [7-10].

There are studies on the use of EVs obtained from different sources in the treatment of various diseases, diagnostics, vaccine studies, and also as drug delivery systems. Yavuz et al. showed that Wharton's jelly mesenchymal stem cells (WJ-MSCs) derived dopamine transporter system was highly effective and did not affect fibroblast viability [11]. Another study also showed that exosomes may be effective in treating diabetic retinopathy [12].

In recent years, plant-based homes have been attracting particular attention. There is increasing interest in this field, as there are many medicinal plants in the world and the biomolecules contained in these plants are positively received for their effectiveness in treating various diseases [13-20].

Researchers first discovered vesicles emerging from the cell in 1967 when looking at cells taken from carrots under an electron microscope. It was later discovered that these were plant-derived EVs. These vesicles were discovered before mammalian EVs, and although they have similar properties, they differ in the composition of their metabolites. According to recent studies, the positive anti-inflammatory and antitumor effects of plant-derived EVs, unlike those of animal-derived EVs, are considered to be minimally harmful [21].

They are not detected by the immune system by their nature and have higher bioactivity compared to mesenchymal stem cells [22,23].

To date, researchers have obtained plant-derived EVs from different plants and fruits. Due to their non-immunogenicity, low toxicity, high delivery efficiency, and good biocompatibility, plant-derived EVs have been found to play an important role in the delivery of

intracellular substances such as nucleic acids, active lipids, and cellular proteins. EV is considered safe because it can be obtained from most edible fruits and vegetables and plants, and has attracted considerable attention in the treatment of various diseases [24-26].

Plant-derived EVs are usually isolated and purified from different parts of plants based on their physicochemical properties. The main methods are ultracentrifugation, sucrose density gradient centrifugation, ultrafiltration centrifugation, polymer precipitation, chromatography, and microfluidic separation technology.

In this article, we analyzed the literature studies we collected on EVs obtained from tea, grapefruit, lemon, grapes, ginger, and aloe plants.

Tea-origin Evs

Tea is not just a soothing drink, it is also beneficial for health. It is rich in antioxidants and strengthens the immune system. Natural compounds in tea, such as caffeine, catechins, and flavonoids, support heart health by lowering cholesterol and improving blood circulation. Tea also contains polyphenol compounds that have antioxidant, antiviral, and anti-inflammatory effects, modulate detoxification enzymes, stimulate immune function, and reduce platelet aggregation.

For this reason, researchers have focused on the medical use of EVs obtained from the tea plant [27]. The effect of EVs derived from tea plants on the intestine was investigated. In 2024, a group of scientists conducted studies on mice and found that tea-derived EVs were able to effectively protect intestinal immune function by increasing IL22 levels. In addition, it significantly increased the levels of antimicrobial peptides such as Reg3g, which effectively protected the intestines from bacteria [28-32].

Another study showed that EVs derived from tea leaves were effective in preventing breast cancer development through pro-apoptosis and microbiota modulation. In vitro studies have shown that tea-derived EVs are effectively taken up by breast cancer cells (4T1 cells), leading to a 2.5-fold increase in intracellular reactive oxygen species. It has been reported to cause mitochondrial damage and cell cycle arrest in tumor cells within 8 hours, leading to tumor cell apoptosis [33,34].

Grapefruit-derived EVs

Grapefruit is rich in various compounds such as vitamin C, vitamin A, potassium, fiber, and antioxidants. Contains Vitamin C: Supports the immune system. It also contains vitamin A, which provides vision and skin regeneration, and fibers regulate the digestive system. The potassium it contains is important for supporting blood pressure and muscle function. These ingredients support overall health by helping to reduce cell damage.

Research has shown that EV derived from grapefruit is rich in phosphatidyl-ethanol-amine and phosphatidyl-choline. Both lipids have been found to have antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anticolic effects [35,36]. Naringin is the main flavonoid found in grapefruit. It has been shown that intestinal microflora can hydrolyze naringin to its functional component naringenin. Naringenin has anticancer, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and anticolic effects and has a wide range of pharmacological properties [37,38]. Studies

have shown that uptake of grapefruit-derived EV by intestinal macrophages induces expression of the HO-1 antioxidant gene and inhibits the production of proinflammatory cytokines.

In another study, grapefruit-derived EVs were shown to target macrophages in the colon, inhibit the production of oxygenase-1 (HO-1), interleukin-10 (IL-10), interleukin-6 (IL-6), and TNF alpha, and reduce lesions in the colon [39].

Lemon-origin Evs

Citric acid, which is contained in the lemon plant, forms the basis of the fruit, while the lemon peel is rich in flavonoids, essential oils, pectin compounds, and dietary fiber. Lemon contains many vitamins. Among them, folic acid and vitamin C, pantothenic acid, vitamin D, tocopherol, thiamine, retinol, pyridoxine, riboflavin, and PP vitamins occupy a special place.

Vitamin C is a powerful antioxidant that protects against cell damage caused by free radicals, strengthens the immune system, and improves skin health. The main fiber in lemons is pectin. Pectin supports digestive health and helps regulate blood sugar. Considering its rich composition, EV has also been obtained from the lemon plant.

Raimondo et al. investigated the use of EVs derived from Citrus limon juice in the treatment of chronic myeloid leukemia (CML) [40]. Lemon-derived EV was found to slow tumor growth in a CML model with an intended targeting effect. TNF- α -related apoptosis-inducing ligand (TRAIL) has also been shown to inhibit the secretion of numerous cytokines associated with angiogenesis. Based on in vivo studies, it has been determined that EVs target tumor tissue within 15 minutes and their effects last for more than 24 hours. Thus, they showed that EVs derived from lemons act as chemotherapeutic agents and help destroy cancer cells.

Grape-origin EVs

Grapes are rich in sugar, cellulose, organic acids, ascorbic acid, vitamins A, B1, B2, B6, PP, C, etc., pectin, microelements and enzymes. Grapevine leaves contain a large amount of vitamin C, carotene, organic acids, etc. Grape skin is primarily composed of flavonoids, phenolic compounds, and stilbenes (resveratrol). Like other fruits and vegetables, grapes are a rich source of fiber and water. Grapes contain well-known antioxidants such as vitamin C and manganese, as well as lesser-known antioxidants such as beta-carotene and resveratrol. Due to its chemical composition, grapes are somewhat similar to breast milk. Thus, three vitamins in grapes are directly related to the blood and hematopoietic system: folic acid (a vitamin belonging to group B) strengthens hematopoiesis; vitamin K has a positive effect on the blood clotting system; vitamin P strengthens the walls of blood vessels and regulates blood pressure.

Researchers have applied EVs derived from grape juice to liver diseases. It has been found that EV from grapes acts as an excellent hepatoprotective agent, suppressing inflammatory processes and chemokine production, as well as reducing macrophage infiltration into the liver. It was found to reduce the persistence of the pro-inflammatory phenotype through inhibition of dual receptors (CCR2/CCR5). Furthermore, grape-de-

rived EVs inhibited the activation of inflammation resulting from macrophage recruitment and induced autophagy, which in turn prevented liver injury induced by lipopolysaccharides (LPS/D-GalN) [41].

In another study conducted on mice, EV isolated from grape juice diffused into intestinal stem cells in mice, upregulated stem cell markers (i.e., SOX2, Oct4, and Klf4), thereby maintaining homeostasis, and accelerated and restored absorption in the gastrointestinal epithelium, and was found to have anti-inflammatory effects [42].

Grapes are high in phenolic compounds, which is why they are considered a natural antioxidant and have a positive effect on the functioning of the blood vascular system. But these features have not been applied or researched as EVs.

Ginger-derived Evs

Ginger (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe) is one of the most common and widely used plants. It is rich in various chemical constituents, including phenolic compounds, terpenes, polysaccharides, lipids, organic acids, crude fibers, and essential oils. The health benefits of ginger are mainly attributed to its phenolic compounds, such as gingerol and chagallol. Studies have shown that ginger has many therapeutic effects, including antioxidant, neuroprotective, cardiovascular and respiratory system protection, as well as anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, anti-obesity, anti-diabetic, and anti-nausea and vomiting effects.

In 2016, a group of scientists studied the effects of EVs derived from edible ginger on colitis-related intestinal inflammation and cancer. In a study conducted on various mice, it was found that EVs derived from ginger contain high amounts of lipids and proteins. These EVs are readily taken up by the intestinal flora, and their miRNAs exert gene effects on specific bacteria, thereby influencing gene regulation and strengthening the intestinal defense system in mice. This can also prevent chronic colitis and colitis-associated cancer (CAC) by improving intestinal microflora.

Ginger-derived EV administration has been shown to reduce inflammatory cytokines (TNF- α , IL-6, and IL-1 β) and increase anti-inflammatory cytokines (IL-10 and IL-22) in colitis, demonstrating improved survival and growth in mice [43-45]. Thus, EV derived from ginger may reduce acute colitis, contain large amounts of non-toxic active ingredients that help restore intestinal flora, and prevent colon cancer.

This study found that EVs derived from ginger can help with healing by repairing damage.

In another study, EV from the ginger plant was added to the water of obese mice. When examining the results obtained, it was revealed that these EVs can protect Foxa2 from phosphorylation by Akt-1 and subsequent inactivation of Foxa2 by enhancing the effect of the Foxa2 gene (a gene found in humans and other mammals that acts as a transcription factor). Increased Foxa2 gene has been shown to alter the composition of intestinal epithelial cells in mice fed ginger-derived EVs and protect against obesity by preventing insulin resistance.

In this study, EVs administered to mice extended the lifespan of the mice and also prevented skin inflammation [46].

Despite ginger's other positive medicinal properties, the effects of EVs derived from it have not been fully studied.

Aloe vera-derived Evs

Aloe vera is widely used in the cosmetic, food and medical industries due to its anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and antibacterial effects. Several studies have shown that Aloe vera contains various phenolic compounds, including cinnamic acids, chromones, anthracene, and flavonoids. In particular, Aloe vera peels have stronger antioxidant activity than other parts (flowers, gel, and roots). The Aloe vera plant has many pharmacological activities, such as antioxidant, antimicrobial, immune-boosting, anticancer, hypoglycemic, hypolipidemic, wound healing, and antidiabetic. Studies have focused mainly on the antioxidant and wound healing potential of EVs derived from Aloe vera peels. The antioxidant effect of EVs derived from Aloe vera plant was evaluated by superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity and cellular antioxidant activity (CAA) assay. Wound healing potential was evaluated in vitro using human keratinocytes (HaCaT) and fibroblasts (HDF). Aloe vera-EVs showed good cytocompatibility in human skin cells and were internalized into HaCaT cells via clathrin and caveolae. Aloe vera-EVs showed good cytocompatibility in human skin cells and were internalized into HaCaT cells via clathrin and caveolae. SOD activity and CAA assays revealed that Aloe vera-EVs exhibited antioxidant activity and dose-dependently reduced intracellular ROS levels in HaCaT cells upon exposure to H₂O₂ [47]. Studies have shown that Aloe vera-EVs have a positive effect on antioxidant defense mechanisms and wound healing by activating the Nrf2 protein.

In another study, Aloe vera-EVs exhibited effective antioxidant activity against oxidative stress in HaCaT cells exposed to H₂O₂ through activation of Nrf2. The antioxidant effect of EV A has been demonstrated for the treatment of diseases caused by oxidative stress and, in particular, for skin regeneration [48]. In general, although the anti-cancer effects of EVs obtained from Aloe vera peels have been investigated in various skin diseases (acne, eczema, and psoriasis), diabetic wounds, and in cancer, studies in this field are new and more research is needed.

Discussion

Based on our literature review, we identified the antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, antioxidant, antimicrobial, immune-enhancing, hypoglycemic, hypolipidemic, wound healing, and antidiabetic effects of plant-derived EVs. The conducted analyses revealed the antibacterial and anticancer effects of EVs obtained from tea plants. EVs derived from grapefruit and lemon plants showed antioxidant, antimicrobial, and immunomodulatory effects. EVs derived from grapevine plants acted as hepatoprotective agents and showed anti-inflammatory effects. EVs from the ginger plant showed anti-inflammatory, anticancer, and anti-hyperglycemic effects. EVs extracted from Aloe Vera plants have been shown to have antioxidant effects and aid wound healing. Although EVs from these plants are known to have therapeutic properties against many diseases, their unexplored positive and negative effects are still being studied.

Conclusion

Although numerous studies have been conducted on the properties and therapeutic efficacy of plant-derived EVs, unfortunately, many aspects of these vesicles have not yet been fully explored. The active components of most plants have not yet been identified and evaluated. Although the positive effects of plant-based EVs have been studied, their side effects are unknown. As we know, they have a nanoscale structure and when applied to diseases, they reach the focus of the disease, but their effect on surrounding cells has not been fully studied. Therefore, further studies and clinical trials are needed to increase research on the bioactivities and applications of BMEVs. We hope that in the future, EVs derived from new medicinally important plants will have a significant impact on the treatment of many diseases, and their side effects will also be studied.

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